

Synthesis, characterization and characteristics of waste-palmolein oil-based alkyd resins and their blend with epoxy resin

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The aim of this work is the valorization of waste palmolein oil. To attain the goal, the waste oil was purified and then converted to alkyd resin, by the two stage alcoholysis-polyesterification process. In the first stage the triglyceride was converted to monoglyceride by transesterification reaction with glycerol. The monoglyceride was then reacted with phthalic anhydride and/or maleic anhydride to synthesize the alkyd. The alkyd was then cured at 120°C in presence of epoxy to produce cured blend of alkyd and epoxy. It was then evaluated by assessing the adhesion, pencil hardness, gloss, thermal stability and chemical resistance, for possible coating applications. The values obtained for all these properties indicated positively for end use in coating applications.

Keywords: Waste palmolein oil, alcoholysis-polyesterification, polycondensation, alkyd resin.

Introduction

There has been a growing awareness and alarm on the finite and depleting nature of petroleum resources. It has become a cause of concern because the petroleum is the mother of all organic chemicals including polymers. So, there is a concerted search for an alternative source and the main target is biomass. Further, the linear route of production which is based on the tenet extract → use → discard is considered as the main reason for resource crunch, environmental degradation and generation of unmanageable amount of waste of diverse nature. Such realizations resulted in the propagation of the idea of circular economy in general and circular chemistry in particular^{1,2}. In the circular model, waste is considered as a highly useful resource. Waste as a resource cannot and must not be ignored if the aim is to achieve circularity of the resources and sustainability³.

Waste vegetable oil generated during cooking, constitute an important resource. It is reported that about 378 million L of waste cooking oil are produced per day in USA alone. Canada, European countries and UK are reported to produce 1,35000, 7,00000–10,00000 and 2,00000 tons of waste cooking oil per year respectively⁴. India consumes 22 mil-

lion tons of vegetable oil annually, producing about three to four million tons of waste cooking oil per year⁵. As the left-over oil after cooking has no food value, it is immensely important to find ways to produce value added products from it. The huge amount of waste cooking oil generated per year has already caught the attention of the industry. At present, the major use of waste cooking oil is in the energy sector for the production of bio-diesel^{6–9}. However, there is a great potential for the use of waste cooking oil in the paint and coating industry as well. This is because; the vegetable oils had been in use in the production of alkyds^{10–14}, for use in paint and coating formulations. Alkyds have several good attributes as coating materials such as strength, rapid drying, good adhesion, flexibility, gloss, good surface wetting, good penetration and good weathering behaviour¹⁵. The present work describes the use of waste palmolein oil as a feedstock for the synthesis of alkyds, their characterization and investigation on the characteristics for coating applications of its blend with epoxy resin.

Materials

Waste palmolein oil (WPO) was collected from the hotels near Gauhati University campus, Guwahati, Assam, India.